

EUDRES² Ent-r-e-novators | List of all metadata on project's datasets

Work Package(s) and Task(s)	Filename	Sheet's name	Dataset name	Relevant WP(s)
WP1 T1.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.1 contact list	List of team members and contacts	All WP
WP1 T1.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.1 financial	Project financial data	All WP
WP1 T1.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.1 monitoring	Monitoring indicators	All WP
WP1 T1.2	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.2 meeting presentations	Presentations in project's meetings	All WP
WP1 T1.2	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.2 meeting attendance lists	Attendance in project's meetings	All WP
WP1 T1.2	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.2 agendas	Agendas of the project's meetings	All WP
WP1 T1.4	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.4 comms and diss activitie	Communication and dissemination activities	All WP
WP1 T1.4	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.4 analytics	Communication analytics	All WP
WP1 T1.4	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.4 Videos	Video series	All WP
WP1 T1.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.5 Registration SP conf	Registration list Science Policy conference	All WP
WP1 T1.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.5 Attendance SP conf	Attendance Science Policy conference	All WP
WP1 T1.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.5 Programme SC conf	Programme Science Policy conference	All WP
WP1 T1.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	T1.5 Presentations SC conf	Presentations of the Science Policy Conference held at	All WP
WP1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP1.xlsx	poster results wp1	Poster WP1 at EUDRES Autumn Summit	WP1
WP2 T2.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP2.xlsx	T2.1 (1)	Status Quo Analysis - scientific areas and alignment with relevant R&I European policies, priorities and programmes: literature review and technology watch	WP2
WP2 T2.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP2.xlsx	T2.1 (2)	Status Quo Analysis - stakeholders and challenges	WP2
WP2 T2.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP2.xlsx	T2.1 (3)	Status Quo Analysis - collaboration in research and innovation within the consortium	WP2
WP2 T2.2	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP2.xlsx	T2.2	SWOT Analysis	WP2
WP2 T2.3	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP2.xlsx	T2.3 (1)	Survey 1	WP2
WP2 T2.3	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP2.xlsx	T2.3 (2)	Survey 2	WP2
WP1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP2.xlsx	poster results wp2	Poster WP2 at EUDRES Autumn Summit	WP2
WP3 T3.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP3.xlsx	Task 3.1-questionnaire database	Research Infrastructure Questionnaire Survey Dataset (responses from 520 researchers)	WP3
WP3 T3.2	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP3.xlsx	Task 3.2 - Internal RI dataset	Internal research infrastructure	WP3
WP3 T3.3	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP3.xlsx	Task 3.3 - External RI dataset	External research infrastructure	WP3
WP3 T3.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP3.xlsx	Task 3.5 - FMEA Risk Analysis	List of risks (FMEA methodology)	WP3
WP3 T3.6, T3.7	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP3.xlsx	Task 3.6 - curated RI dataset	Strategic RI dataset	WP3
WP3	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP3.xlsx	poster results wp3	Poster WP3 at EUDRES Autumn Summit	WP3
WP4 T4.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP4.xlsx	Survey on policies	Survey on OS/OI/OE policies	WP4
WP4 T4.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP4.xlsx	training materials	Set of training materials for workshops, webinars and summer school on OS/EI/OE	WP4
WP4	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP4.xlsx	poster results wp4	Poster WP4 at EUDRES Autumn Summit	WP4
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Knowledge clips WP5	Citizen Science Knowledge clips	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Game scavenger hunt	Citizen Science Scavenger hunt	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Game citizen science stairs	Game citizen science stairs	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Maturity model	Maturity model with 8 key competence areas and 4 levels based on the EURAXESS Researcher Profiles	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast of D5,1	Podcast 'Deliverables Dialogues - From Enthusiastic Amateurs to engaged experts mastering citizen science'	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast D5,5 UPT	Podcast 'Creating communities, engaging citizens and society'	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast D5,5 UPT ex	Podcast 'Creating communities, engaging citizens and society' - examples	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast D5,5 UCLL 1	Podcast 'Creating communities, engaging citizens and society' - UCLL	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast D5,5 UCLL 2	Podcast 'Creating communities, engaging citizens and society' - findings of participants of training	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast D5,5 UCLL 3	Podcast 'Creating communities, engaging citizens and society' - approach of training Citizen Science at UCLL	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast D5,5 STPUAS	Podcast 'Creating communities, engaging citizens and society' - STPUAS	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles VIA 1	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - ViA (1)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles VIA 2	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - ViA (2)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles UPT 1	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - UPT (1)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles UPT 2	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - UPT (2)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles STPUAS 1	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - STPUAS (1)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles STPUAS 2	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - STPUAS (2)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles IPS 1	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - IPS (1)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles IPS 2	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - IPS (2)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles UCLL1	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - UCLL (1)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles UCLL2	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - UCLL (2)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles MATE1	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - MATE (1)	WP5
WP5 T5.5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Podcast CS chronicles MATE2	Podcast 'Citizen Science Chronicles series' - MATE (2)	WP5
WP5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	Paper enhancing CS Engagement	Paper 'Enhancing Citizen Science Engagement	WP5
WP5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	CS Toolkit	Citizen Science Toolkit	WP5
WP5	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP5.xlsx	poster results wp5	Poster WP5 at EUDRES Autumn Summit	WP5
WP6 T6.1	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP6.xlsx	survey	Survey on the institutions' policies, practices and procedures regarding scientific employment	WP6
WP6	ENTRN MD Entrenovators WP6.xlsx	poster results wp6	Poster WP6 at EUDRES Autumn Summit	WP6